

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

COLD TOLERANCE

Agronomic traits of cold-tolerant rices

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In 1984, we evaluated 90 transplanted rice varieties for cold tolerance at Upper Shillong Farm (elevation 1900 m). Temperatures were low from panicle initiation through harvest. Entries included local and improved indicas and japonicas.

Maximum and minimum values for agronomic traits are in the table. K 332 had minimum days to 50% flowering; Namyi for minimum flag leaf angle; and Chhanapaddy for minimum grain sterility. The three are indica varieties.

There were significant positive relationships between grain yield and plant height (0.477), effective tillers per plant (0.321), flag leaf angle (0.387), grains per panicle (0.726), and harvest index (0.602). Percent sterility and grain yield were significantly and negatively

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Character	Range		Mean	Correlation coefficient with grain yield ^a
	Minimum	Maximum		
Days to 50% flowering	121 (K332)	170 (Khamang, Kba-saw rit B ₂ & B ₄)	159.31	0.224
Plant height (cm)	60 (K332)	110 (Zichum)	88.77	0.477**
Leaf area index	1.84 (Ryllo red)	6.70 (PK2-26-1)	3.27	0.143
Tillers per plant	4 (Kba-sawrit B ₄)	16 (PK2-26-1)	7.91	0.207
Effective tillers per plant	4 (Kba-saw rit B ₄)	16 (PK2-26-1)	7.38	0.321*
Flag leaf angle (°)	70 (Namyi)	115 (PK2-3-1)	63.27	0.387**
Panicle length (cm)	15 (K-333)	24 (Dullo-8, CH-1039)	20.73	0.238
Grains per panicle	2.3 (Muzudo)	84.4 (Ryllo red A)	42.61	0.726**
Sterility (%)	27 (Chhanapaddy)	98 (Muzudo)	52.30	-0.594**
Harvest index	0.01 (Borkat)	0.70 (Ryllo red 6)	0.35	0.602**
Grain yield (t/ha)	(1.0 (Borkat)	2.5 (PK2-26-1)	0.91	

^aSignificant at 1% (**), and 5% (*) levels

related (-0.594).

PK2-26-1, Ryllo red A, and Namyi

may be suitable donors for cold tolerance breeding programs. *ℓ*

Cold tolerance of Yunnan rices at different elevations

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We tested 105 rice varieties from Yunnan Province for cold tolerance at early seedling, seedling, booting, and flowering stages at the Institute of Crop Germplasm Resources, Beijing.

Hei-Gu, Wu-Chew-Ma-Xian-Gu, Hong-Mang-Da-Ding, and Bi-Jing no. 7 had greatest cold tolerance at all stages. Bi-Gu, Lao-Lai-Hong, Bang-Tou-Nuo, Xiao-Ai-Jiao-Nuo, Da-Bai-Gu, Ziao-Hoang-Gu, Huang-La-Gu, Shi-Li-Xiang, Hai-Gu, Jiu-Gu, Han-Gu, Yu-Gu, and Lao-Lai-Bai had cold tolerance at flowering.

Correlation between cold tolerance and elevation at which rice varieties are planted.

Cold tolerance at early seedling, seedling, and flowering stages were

highly and significantly correlated with the elevation at which they were planted.